

BIOMATRIX FIELD TEST:

Preliminary Phenology Study on Bioreceptive Substrate Elements for Increased Urban Biodiversity

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ABSTRACT

Urban areas, often considered devoid of significant ecological value, have emerged as crucial habitats for biodiversity. This research explores the potential of urban environments to support a high level of biodiversity and investigates innovative approaches to urban design that can enhance this ecological potential. Focusing on the BioMatrix elements, a novel porous typology of concrete produced through the use of ice as the molding material, the study examines its ecological benefits in urban settings. The research draws from a field test in Zurich, to assess the effectiveness of these structures in promoting urban biodiversity. This preliminary report assesses the phenology of approx. 20 plant species during the period of 6 month. The findings underscore the promising properties of BioMatrix as a urban design tool for mitigating biodiversity loss.

1. INTRODUCTION

Biodiversity is in a steep decline globally, including in Switzerland (BAFU, 2023). Urbanization and intensive agricultural practices have drastically cut back natural habitats, with more than 95% of pastures and grasslands disappearing over the past century (Hallmann C.A et al.,2017). As cities expand, integrating the needs of plants and animals into urban planning becomes essential to mitigate further losses. A high biodiversity is crucial to improve the stability of the ecosystems and the cities' resilience to the impacts of climate change. Ecosystems and natural infrastructure serve as barriers to climate-related hazards, playing a role in managing the impacts of climate and safeguarding urban populations and infrastructure (C40 Knowledge Community, 2023).

Historically, cities were not inherently antithetical to biodiversity. Urban areas in Switzerland are home to a remarkably high number of species, approximately 40% of all native animal species and 45% of native vascular plants of the country can be found in cities. It is estimated that over 10,000 different species of animals are present in the city of Zurich (BAFU, 2023) (Ineichen S./Ruckstuhl M./Hose S., 2022). Cities provide numerous suitable habitats for wild animals, driven by an abundant food supply, a warmer microclimate, and the presence of small-scale, varied green spaces. Furthermore, urban areas frequently host a mix of native and non-native plants introduced intentionally or accidentally by humans. This diverse flora can support a broader array of herbivores, pollinators, and other species compared to the uniform crops in agricultural fields. Consequently, many species migrate from surrounding areas into urban settings. This migration also reflects the ongoing loss of natural habitats in rural regions, positioning cities as alternative habitats for displaced wildlife (Grün Stadt Zürich, 2014).

New urban developments, however, often overlook the needs of biodiversity. The energy optimization of buildings, for example, has led to more compact and closed façades, eliminating the nooks and fissures where many species of birds and small mammals sought shelter. The scarcity of nesting sites is a major problem especially for birds, which is leading to a decline in species diversity in urban areas (Tschäpperle S./ Haslinger A., 2021). Other characteristics of urban areas pose a challenge for animal and plant life, such as the extensive sealing of floor surfaces, large glass fronts, light pollution, traffic, noise, as well as the intensive upkeep and uniform design of private gardens and public spaces (BAFU, 2023) (Lepczyk C.A. et al., 2017).

There are several design principles that can help enhance urban biodiversity by providing essential habitats. Architectural features such as niches in building exteriors can offer breeding sites for birds and roosting spots for bats. A prominent example of the design-integrated biodiversity can be found in the methodology developed by the architecture studio Chartier-Dalix, with complex design solutions which offer habitat for vegetation and animals (Chartier et al., 2019). Additionally, the greening of façades and roofs supports a diverse range of species, including snails, spiders, and insects, which thrive in these vertical green spaces (Grün Stadt Zürich, 2014). These design elements of urban environment could be crucial in connecting habitats and provide “stepping stones” for animals to move through the city (Hagenauer M./ Balducci A., 2024).

This paper is aimed to address the design principles of bio-receptive structures which could deliver a space-saving and highly performing solution for intensifying urban biodiversity. The study is based on an innovative technology IceFormwork, which allows low-tech fabrication method for geometrically complex spatially graded structures of mineral binders. In particular, the technology is used for production of a bio-receptive substrate structure called BioMatrix, a porous concrete elements with unique qualities of large-scale interconnected pores. The system utilizes ice as a temporary mold for controlled forming of interconnected cavities in concrete. This method leverages the unique material intelligence of ice to create complex topology.

2. METHODOLOGY

The BioMatrix system studied here as a bio-receptive substrate structure for increased urban biodiversity is using Ice Formwork fabrication method. The innovative fabrication process involves a reusable shuttering of a simple rectangular form that is filled with processed pieces of ice, forming interconnected cavities in the BioMatrix structure. (fig. 1) (Sitnikov et al., 2022) This process is performed in a refrigerated environment to avoid melting of ice during the casting. The demoulding process is autonomous and requires no manual labour: once the concrete has been cast and set, the ice melts away, autonomously revealing a finished concrete element. The meltwater aids in curing the concrete by maintaining moisture levels during the early stages of hydration. The technology relies on developments in antifreeze admixtures that enable hydration of mineral binder and strength gain at negative temperatures. (Sitnikov and Sitnikov, 2018)

To evaluate the environmental rationality of BioMatrix use as the bio-receptive substrate we need to look into several aspects of this concrete structure, namely geometrical, chemical, and ecological properties. This evaluation is the first part of the study and goes under title “Environmental Metrics”.

Secondly, it is important to understand the performance of the BioMatrix, and the effect it can produce on the biodiversity. This is a challenging question for that the collection of data required for reliable conclusions requires minimum of 4 year study. Given that this paper is published in the first year of the biodiversity research, the analysis will be performed using partial data from 6 month phenology observations, and goes under title “Phenological Observations”.

Finally, in the third part of the study we are discussing a design system for urban biodiversity infrastructure based on BioMatrix and informed with our environmental calculations and derived experimental data. This chapter goes under title “Design Case Study”.

Figure 1:
The BioMatrix prototype used for the field test. Dimensions: 120x120x90cm, 800kg.

2.1. ENVIRONMENTAL METRICS

The BioMatrix allows for the creation of complex and organic shapes that are challenging to achieve with traditional formwork materials or additive fabrication. The interconnected cavities developed spatially throughout the volume have refined geometry thanks to material intelligence and self-organization of ice. While state-of-the-art particle-bed 3D printers may reproduce this topological structure, the fidelity of the details at large fabrication scale would be economically irrational. Thanks to the mechanical bulk processing of ice used in the Ice Formwork process, the fabrication of BioMatrix can be rapidly scaled and comparably low cost due to repurposing of existing industrial machinery.

2.1.1. ENERGY USE

Though ice is an advantageous ecological substitute for traditional concrete formwork material, the embodied energy of ice can be quite high if produced artificially. When using existing ice block generators, the energy consumption can be somewhere between 80-150 kWh per cubic meter. For comparison, a cubic meter of construction wood boards or plywood is somewhere between 500-2000 kWh.

The ice used in the fabrication, however, can come from the industrial waste, further reducing the production energy. Fish industry, or hockey stadiums, produce significant amount of ice waste on a regular basis. The production of the experimental prototypes featured here have used ice waste from a local hockey stadium.

2.1.2. CARBON FOOTPRINT

BioMatrix is produced using mineral binders, as they outperform other materials in terms of availability, affordability and durability. However, the downside of some mineral binders, such as Portland cement, is the high carbon footprint of approximately 1 ton of carbon released per ton of cement. Due to relatively simple casting process of Ice Formwork method, the technology allows to use sustainable cement supplements, reducing the carbon footprint down to 0.4 tons per ton of binder, which is enough to produce 4 m³ of BioMatrix structure. For a rough CO₂ accounting we can take that herbaceous plants capture approximately 2.5kg/m² of land area per annum. Due to the spatial structure of BioMatrix we can at least expect the green area to 2m² per each square meter of footprint area. With these very modest expectations, the 400 kg of carbon footprint will be recaptured over the period of 20 years, which is much shorter then lifetime of BioMatrix.

2.1.3. GEOMETRICAL PROPERTIES

The geometrical qualities and benefits of BioMatrix are uncanny and need to be defined here. The relative density of the structure is about 600-800 kg/m³, while the material itself is a durable mineral composition with density of 2,300 kg/m³, which takes less then 30% of the volume. That is, with every cubic meter of mineral binder BioMatrix delivers around 4 m³ of inhabitable space for flora and fauna, . Furthermore, since the forming martial is spread out in space forming large, interconnected cavities, it provide an extensive exposed surface area. With finer cavity size of 5-10 cm, the exposed surface area can reach 20 m² per 1 m³ of BioMatrix; with larger cavities of 25-30 cm the exposed surface area reduces to 10m².

2.1.4. THE PH ENVIRONMENT OF PLANTS

Speaking of the use case of BioMatrix in the biodiversity field, the substrate suitability for the plants needs to be mentioned. It is known that due to the high content of calcium silicates, calcium aluminates, and calcium hydroxides conventional concrete is highly alkalic, approximately 12-13 pH. Such high alkalinity is not compatible with vegetation, and usually requires decades of carbonation to neutralize the alkali environment of the exposed surface. The special blend of concrete created for IceFormwork, however, has lower alkalinity, which carries no structural risks due to absence of steel reinforcement.

Once the BioMatrix has been produced and exposed to the outdoor weather condition, its surface reaches values lower than 8 pH after in 28 days and is able to support rapid colonisation by algae and moths. (fig 2)

Figure 2:
Macro photograph of a laboratory test of BioMatrix suitability for lithophytes and bryophytes plants.

2.2. PHENOLOGICAL OBSERVATIONS

The objective of the phenological study was to identify the suitable types of plants for autonomous and successive colonisation of the BioMatrix structure. While as a habitat BioMatrix is closest to the drystone walls and ruderal areas, its properties are more complicated due to deep shaded core of ventilated space, thus experimental study was of major interest. The critical aspect of survival of the plants on these structures can be ruled out as lack of water due to effective draining, and lack of nutritious substrate. In order to conduct an evaluation of the vegetable compatibility, we have designed a very challenging experimental rig: no artificial irrigation and a south-oriented location with high solar exposure. The experimental rig was put in place in April 2024 and observed monthly until October 2024.

Figure 3:
Field test design.
1 - scheme of the test rig in the 1st month of the test;
2 - view of the test rig on the 6th month of the test;
3 - scheme of the difference in the soil substrate distribution in the prototypes.

Figure 3 illustrates the different arrangement of two examined BioMatrix designs: the low one with continuous soil filling connected to the ground, and thus able to hold water for longer; and the high one, where upper levels of structure were holding small amounts of humus, disconnected from the ground, and thus providing mainly dry substrate.

The phenological observation counted 24 species of different plants. The plants were planted or sowed in April during the installation of the rig, but during experiment several local weeds have partly invaded the experimental setup and therefore have also been included in the observation. Table 1 lists the species according to their sunlight requirement and specifies their dependence on water and soil.

The phenological observation shows, that the plants that thrived most on the biomatrix are either desert inhabiting herbaceous and succulents, which loved to dwell on the dry, warm and sunny stoney upper surfaces of the structure, and shadow and moist loving ivies and ferns, which found habitat on the shaded sides and in the deeper cavities of the BioMatrix.

Figure 4:
Excerpt from documentation of plant species growth rate and pollination monitoring.
1-glechoma hederacea;
2-sedum album;
3-petrosedum rupestre;
4-saxifragia rosacea;
5-clarkia unguiculata;
6-nigella damascene;
7-eschscholiza californica;
8-clarkia amoena.

The observation also shows that 8 plant species suffered draft stress between 98 and 125 days of the experiment. The table 2 provides meteorological record, which documents extremely dry and sunny weather of 4th period. The draft mainly concerned pollinating plants, and occurred after their pollination phase, providing that they may have as well transitioned to fertilisation stage. This argument can be supported by the second pollination of Eschscholzia Californica, which took place in late September.

Plant Specie	Type	General plant requirements			Day of phenological observations					
		Sunlight (0-10)	Water (0-10)	Soil (0-10)	0	27	57	98	125	169
Eschscholzia californica	Herb.	9	3	4	swd	1	2	3	4	3
Eschscholzia caespitosa	Herb.	9	3	4	swd	1	2	3	5	5
Petrosedum rupestre	Succ.	9	2	4	plnt	2	2	2	2	2
Sonchus asper	Herb.	8	4	7	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	2
Linum grandiflorum	Herb.	8	5	5	swd	1	2	3	5	5
Sedum album	Succ.	8	3	4	N/A	plnt	3	2	2	2
Rosmarin prostratus	Per.	8	3	6	N/A	plnt	2	2	2	2
Malcolmia maritima	Herb.	8	6	6	swd	2	3	4	4	4
Lobularia maritima	Herb.	7	5	5	swd	1	2	3	5	5
Calendula officinalis	Herb.	7	5	5	swd	1	2	3	5	5
Clarkia amoena	Herb.	7	5	5	swd	1	2	3	5	5
Nigella damascena	Herb.	7	5	5	swd	1	2	3	5	5
Pelargonium peltatum	Ivy	7	6	5	N/A	2	3	5	5	5
Clarkia unguiculata	Herb.	7	5	5	swd	1	2	3	5	5
Saxifraga cespitosa	Per.	6	5	7	plnt	3	4	4	4	4
Cymbalaria muralis	Ivy	6	4	6	plnt	2	3	5	5	5
Galium mollugo	Ivy	5	5	6	plnt	2	2	2	2	2
Deschampsia cespitosa	Herb.	5	6	8	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	2
Glechoma hederacea	Ivy	5	4	7	N/A	plnt	2	2	2	2
Hedera helix	Ivy	4	4	7	N/A	plnt	2	2	2	2
Dryopteris carthusiana	Fern	4	6	8	plnt	2	2	2	2	2
Asplenium scolopendrium	Fern	4	6	8	plnt	2	2	2	2	2
Asplenium trichomanes	Fern	4	6	8	plnt	2	2	2	5	5
Polypodium vulgare	Fern	3	7	8	plnt	2	2	2	2	2

Table 1:
Phenology metrics of the examined species.

Notation:

- 1 - seedling;
- 2 - adult plant;
- 3 - pollination,
- 4 - fertilization;
- 5 - draft stress.

Table 2:
Key meteorological data parameters of the investigated periods based on the data recorded by the closest meteorological station REH Zürich / Affoltern, MeteoSchweiz

#	Period	Days	Daily average values			
			Global radiation	Temp.	Precip.	Sunshine Duration
			W/m ²	°C	mm	h
1	17.04.2024 - 14.05.2024	27	176.1	10.2	2.9	4.0
2	14.05.2024 - 12.06.2024	30	187.6	14.9	6.3	4.1
3	12.06.2024 - 23.07.2024	41	224.8	19.4	4.7	6.0
4	23.07.2024 - 19.08.2024	27	246.3	21.8	1.8	9.3
5	19.08.2024 - 02.10.2024	44	156.2	15.9	4.3	5.1

2.3. BIOMATRIX DESIGN CASE STUDY

The final third part of the study is dedicated to the development of a rationalized design system for the BioMatrix biodiversity use. The authors have developed a design of a bio-active partition wall for “Wilder Platz”, a communal garden in Zurich. The design is based on rectangular BioMatrix blocks stacked to form a 80 cm high fence, with an integrated bench for visitors. The aim of the proposal is to provide a structure that is beneficial to the local ecosystem and can also be enjoyed by the human visitors of the garden.

Due to the topography of the site, it is difficult to use any heavy lifting machinery in the construction. The size of the elements was thus designed ergonomically: the dimension of 20cm x 40cm x 80cm weighs about 50kg – just light enough for two people to transport.

Figure 5:
Visualization of the proposed bio-active wall design.

The blocks are stacked in a stretcher-bond-pattern with a gradual decrease in height towards the short ends. The wall is formed by two parallel layers of blocks with a layer of soil between them, which acts as a moisture reservoir, preventing the soil in the cavities of the BioMatrix from drying out too quickly when precipitation is scarce. It also allows for the planting of bigger plants that provide shading, since the space is exposed to the sun from the southside and there are no existing shading structures, making the space very hot during the day.

The planting strategy is guided by the wall's orientation relative to the sun and it was important to only use local species. On the southern side, blackthorn (*Prunus spinosa*) is utilized to provide natural shading. The wall elements in this sun-exposed area are populated with plant species adapted to dry and sunny conditions (*Stipa pennata*, *Sempervivum Calareum*, *Sedum album*).

In contrast, moisture-loving ferns are planted on the northern side, where they are paired with plants suited to semi-shady environments (*Asplenium trichomanes*, *Sempervivum tectorum*, *Alyssum montanum*).

The intermediate zone between these areas is filled with nutrient-rich substrate, supporting the growth of tall grasses and vibrant flowering plants (*Papaver rheas*, *Centaurea jacobina*, *Physalis alkekengi*). This zone acts as a vertical and natural extension of the fence, with the changing colors of flowers and grasses framing the view into the surrounding wilderness. The concept for plants takes into account the longest blooming time, to provide the maximum nutrition and habitat for the insects on the site.

The design was submitted at the end of June 2024, it was awarded the first place and will be implemented in the spring of 2025.

Figure 6:
Explication of ecosystem regeneration and the interrelation of its actors.

Figure 7:
Section of the site with
notation of spatial limitation.

3. FINDINGS & CONCLUSION

The results of the study show that BioMatrix can be efficiently used as a vegetation substrate to expand the intensity and variety of vegetation on a space-limited areas. The examined plant species have shown good adaptability and long pollination period without any artificial irrigation. The loosely located humus wasn't washed out with heavy rains during the field tests. The succulents, ivies and, surprisingly, ferns, which were planted on the shadowed side of the structure, managed to thrive through the drafty period of the summer 2024. In prospect of future work, more precise quantitative analysis of the BioMatrix effect on biodiversity will need to be established and analysed, potentially involving machine-learning to advance the phenology observation with larger data quantities.

With the resulting design system we intend to demonstrate versatility and simplicity of BioMatrix as a solution to increase and diversify vegetation in dense urban areas. The following research and case study of the project in Wilder Platz will provide more knowledge about the system. Further improvements of the system may require integrating the humus addition in the process of fabrication to reduce intensive manual labore. Potentially, the structure could also integrate passive rain-water collection and preservation system to support the ecosystem during the drafty periods.

REFERENCES

- Bundesamt für Umwelt BAFU/Office fédéral de l'environnement OFEV/
Ufficio federale dell'ambiente UFAM (2023): Biodiversität in der
Schweiz, [online] Available at:
<<https://www.bafu.admin.ch/uz-2306-d>> [Accessed 17. August
2024]
- Hallmann, Caspar A./Martin Sorg/Eelke Jongejans/Henk Siepel/Nick
Hofland/Heinz Schwan/Werner Stenmans/Andreas Müller/
Hubert Sumser/Thomas Hörren/Dave
Goulson/Hans De Kroon (2017): More than 75 percent decline
over 27 years in total flying insect biomass in protected areas,
in: PLoS ONE, Bd. 12, Nr. 10, S. e0185809, [online] Available at:
<<https://journals.plos.org/plosone/article%3Fid=10.1371/journal.pone.0185809>> [Accessed 17. August 2024]
- C40 Knowledge Community (2023): [online] Available at:
<https://www.c40knowledgehub.org/s/article/Why-biodiversity-matters-for-cities-and-the-climate?language=en_US> [Accessed
17. August 2024]
- Ineichen, S., M. Ruckstuhl, and S. Hose. 2022. Neue Stadtfauna: 700
Tierarten der Stadt Zürich, p.9.
- Chartier, F., P. Dalix, and S. Deramond. 2019. *Hosting Life. Architecture
as an Ecosystem*. Paris: Park Books.
- Grün Stadt Zürich (2014): Konzept Arten- und Lebensraumförderung,
[online] Available at: <https://www.stadt-zuerich.ch/content/dam/stzh/ted/Deutsch/gsz_2/publikationen/planung-und-bau/konzepte-und-leitbilder/Konzept_Arten-Lebensraumfoerderung.pdf> [Accessed 17. August 2024]
- Sitnikov, Vasily, Lena Kitani, Artemis Maneka, Ena Lloret-Fritsch,
Juney Lee, and Benjamin Dillenburger. 2022. "Design and
Fabrication of Spatially Graded Concrete Elements with Ice
Aggregate Method." In *Third RILEM International Conference
on Concrete and Digital Fabrication*, edited by Richard Buswell,
Ana Blanco, Sergio Cavalaro, and Peter Kinnell, 78–83. RILEM
Bookseries. Cham: Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-06116-5_12.
- Sitnikov, V., and I. Sitnikov. 2018. "Kinetics of UHPC Strength Gain
at Subfreezing Temperatures." In *ACI Technical Publication:
Durability and Sustainability of Concrete Structures*, SP-326:117.1-
117.8. Moscow: American Concrete Institute.

- Tschäpperle, S., A. Haslinger. 2021. Berner Praxishandbuch Biodiversität – Natur braucht Stadt, p.182, [online] Available at: <<https://www.bern.ch/themen/umwelt-natur-und-energie/stadtnatur/biodiversitaet/natur-braucht-stadt/lebensraeume/nisthilfen/download-kapitel-nisthilfen/berner-praxishandbuch-biodiversitat-nisthilfen.pdf/download>> [Accessed 17. August 2024]
- Lepczyk, C.A. et al. (2017) 'Biodiversity in the City: Fundamental Questions for Understanding the Ecology of Urban Green Spaces for Biodiversity Conservation,' *BioScience*, 67(9), pp. 799–807, [online] Available at: <<https://doi.org/10.1093/biosci/bix079>> [Accessed 17. August 2024]
- Lewandowski, Delphine, Henri Robain, Philippe Clergeau, and Robert Le Roy. 2023. “Bioreceptivity of Living Walls: Interactions between Building Materials and Substrates, and Effect on Plant Growth.” *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening* 83 (May):127912. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ufug.2023.127912>.